

MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM PROTOCOL IN THE TREATMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS

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Niceia Prates Macedo¹

Rebeca Bastos dos Santos Gonçalves¹

Angela Mara Rambo Martini²

Adriane Viapiana Bossa²

Dr. Jefferson Souza Santos³

SUMMARY

Currently, several treatments have been studied in order to restore health. A very promising treatment option is through the use of magnets. The exposure of cells to the Static Magnetic Field (SMF) is able to affect cellular behavior by rebalancing their hydrogen potential (pH) that was previously in dysfunction, and may help control signs and symptoms of diseases resulting from patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) who may present subclinical states of infectious diseases. Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a non-invasive integrative therapy that uses magnets as a tool to rebalance the body's natural pH, allowing the return to normal health conditions. With the MB it is possible to identify and correct dysfunctions that can lead and sustain infectious pathologies, through the protocol proposed by Dr. David Goiz Martínez, assisting in the improvement of signs and symptoms associated with diabetes mellitus, contributing to the

general improvement of the individual. Objective: This study aims to present a MB protocol to aid in the treatment of DM. It also seeks a broad view of other protocols not considered in Martínez's proposal and suggests their incorporation. Materials and Methods: the article is a literary review where 42 references were used, being 05 for the elaboration of the protocol. Results: script of the protocol with the step-by-step treatment of DM with the MB. Conclusion: MB is a complementary and integrative technique with prophylactic potential in metabolic, endocrine and pathogenic disorders, easy to apply, low cost and with relatively fast results, with very low side effects. Future perspectives: It is mandatory to prove the proposed protocol.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic pair; Static Magnetic Field; Diabetes Mellitus; Protocol.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 MAGNETIC FIELD

The human body contains electric fields and magnetic fields (MFs) generated by living matter, through the charges that constitute matter and give each cell the excitability necessary to act and react to stimuli. The presence of surplus charges in cells tends to form a biomagnetic field, making them susceptible to the presence of the Static Magnetic Field (SMF) (MOLINARI *et al.*, 2018; ZHANG *et al.*, 2020).

This sensitivity of a biological system and exposure to these fields can be observed in cell membranes, where cellular behavior will be affected when stimulated by this exposure (MOLINARI *et al.*, 2018; ZHANG *et al.*, 2020; CARTER *et al.*, 2020).

Studies show that therapies with low and medium intensity MSC are tools of beneficial effects used in various clinical practices, assisting in the modulation of cellular metabolism, cell proliferation and apoptosis, and recovery of the nervous system. In addition, these therapies contribute to the improvement of diabetic neuropathy, facilitate the resolution of inflammation, accelerate the healing of

diabetic wounds and increase bone regeneration by aiding in the delay of diabetic osteoarthropathy (ZHANG *et al.*, 2018; SHANG *et al.*, 2019; LI *et al.*, 2020; FENG *et al.*, 2022).

One of the ways that SMF acts on the cell is through the radical pair mechanism. Where the radicals of contrary charges, positive and negative, which are generated by a simultaneous chemical reaction with magnetic properties, rebalances the previously surplus charges, thus modulating the redox system (reduction oxidation reaction) (CRUZ, 2005; MOLINARI *et al.*, 2018; LI *et al.*, 2020; CARTER *et al.*, 2020; FENG *et al.*, 2022).

An important scholar of this field of research was Dr. Richard Broeringmeyer who described the effects of magnetic energy on bodily systems. He observed that the hydrogen potential (pH) of the internal organs can undergo changes in the presence of magnetic fields (DURÁN, 2008).

1.2 MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM

Based on the studies of Broeringmeyer, Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán studied the bioenergetic phenomena produced by microorganisms within living beings (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008). He noted that pathological and pathogenic manifestations form from positive electric poles (+) that are associated with the south magnetic pole, formed by clusters of hydrogen ions (H^+). The negative electric poles (-) are associated with the magnetic north pole, which are formed by clusters of hydroxyl ions (OH^-) and other free radicals that form the Biomagnetic Pair (BMP). This ionic configuration tends to alter the entropy of the organism, generating a decompensation of health as shown in Figure 1 (DURÁN, 2008).

Figure 1: Polarization of the Biomagnetic Pair and its characteristics

Source: Image from the PAR MAGNÉTICO INSTITUTE (IPM) (BOSSA, 2021a).

In the WB convention, the magnetic poles of the magnets are contrary to the magnetic poles of the planet, with the north pole of the magnet, the negative and the south pole, positive relating to the electric charges of the biochemical elements as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Relationship of the poles of the MB magnets with the Earth's magnetic field

NORTH POLE

SOUTH POLE

Subtitle: In the first figure the north pole of the magnet attracts the tip of the compass needle, while in the second the south pole repels the compass needle.

Source: Martínez (2018); Bossa (2021a)

In 1988, Dr. Goiz identified in a patient, with acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, the first BMP composed of well-defined poles through the separation of loads. This phenomenon allowed the identification of pH dysfunctions located in the middle part of the sternum and in the distal part of the coccyx (Figure 3). This BMP was called Thymus/Rectum (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008; FRANK, 2017). The pair's loads were tested by applying SMF generated by magnets. After a few minutes of the pair Thymus/Rectum in contact, it was observed that the loads previously in dysfunction were neutralized. A few days later the patient had no symptoms (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008; FRANK, 2017).

From these observations, Dr. Goiz looked for other BMPs relating each pair to a particular pathology. In this way, Dr. Goiz formed a mapping of pairs that are the basis of biomagnetic and bioenergetic diagnosis and treatment of MB through SMFs (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008; CASTEJÓN, 2015; FRANK, 2017).

Figure 3: Representation of Ionic Polarization in the Thymus/Rectum Biomagnetic Pair

Subtitle: Cluster of hydroxyl ions in the region of the thymus gland and hydrogen in the region of the rectum.

Source: MPI Image (BOSSA, 2021a).

Through the BMP it is possible to identify all the structure involved in the alteration of the pH of the organism, the organ that is generating polarity, the existence of viruses and bacteria present in the environment and the interaction of these with other microorganisms (DURÁN, 2008).

In this way, Dr. Goiz developed a new therapeutic, Medical Biomagnetism, a term modified by him to Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) (DURÁN, 2008). The MB is a non-invasive integrative therapy that uses SMFs generated by medium intensity machines (from 1,000 to 7,500 Gauss or 0.1T to 0.75T) as a tool, generating a field supported by BMP. As a treatment, the excess charges are neutralized in order to rebalance the pH of the region that was in dysfunction through the depolarization of the dysfunctional biomagnetic fields present in the body (BOSSA, 2019; BOSSA, 2021b; DURÁN, 2008; BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

Diseases can be generated by pathogens present in acidic or alkaline regions, from a dysfunction of the local pH, taking advantage of the available “terrain” for their growth and development (DURÁN, 2008; JIMENO, PENA and BAENA, 2014; FRANK, 2017). By re-establishing the homeostasis of the organism, the MB

eliminates the favorable environment for these pathogens. Thus, the organism tends to return its physiological functions normally, restoring health (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2008; JIMENO, PENA and BAENA, 2014).

Some diseases such as diabetes mellitus (DM) are usually associated with infectious diseases, causing the patient to develop, for the most part, a subclinical state of these diseases. With the WB it is possible to identify and correct dysfunctions generated by infectious pathologies, helping to improve the symptoms associated with DM and contributing to the improvement of the quality of life and health of the individuals affected by the disease (DURÁN, 2008).

1.3 DIABETES MELLITUS

According to data released by the International Diabetes Federation (2021) this disease causes one death every five seconds worldwide, totalling 6.7 million deaths in 2021. Currently DM affects 537 million adults, aged between 20 and 79 years, with 32 million in South and Central America (IDF, 2021). Brazil is in 5th place with 16.8 million patients and with an estimated 21.5 million in 2030 (MORESCHI, 2018; IDF, 2021; WHO, 2022). In 90% of cases, diabetes manifests as Type 2, which is related to overweight, obesity and poor lifestyle habits (IDF, 2021).

Map 1: World projection I on Diabetes Mellitus from 2021 to 2045.

Subtitle: Number of people aged 20 to 79 years with DM per region in the world.

Source: (IDF, 2021)

DM is a chronic, non-transmissible metabolic pathology of multiple origins, caused by biological and environmental factors. It is characterized by a hormonal alteration of insulin, maintaining high levels of glucose (sugar) in the blood (TONIOLO *et al.*, 2018; MORESCHI, 2018; GOMES and ACCARDO, 2019; IDF, 2021; WHO, 2022; LUCA, 2019; FENG *et al.*, 2022).

According to the Brazilian Society of Diabetes (SDB, 2022), DM can be classified by 3 types: type 1 diabetes (DM1), type 2 diabetes (DM2) and gestational diabetes (GDM), in addition to subtypes classified according to the clinical characteristics that preceded diabetes: monogenic defects in the function of the *pancreatic* β cell, genetic dysfunction in the action of insulin, diseases of the exocrine pancreas, chemically induced endocrine association, secondary to drugs,

secondary to infections, immune-mediated and genetic syndromes associated with diabetes (RODAKCI, 2022).

Studies show that DM has an important interaction with infectious agents. People affected by this disease are more prone to infections and other comorbidities, causing the patient to develop, for the most part, a subclinical state (TONIOLO *et al.*, 2018). It can also be triggered by a pancreatic dysfunction where the organ loses the function of producing the hormone or when the body is unable to utilize the insulin produced (WHO, 2022; LIMA *et al.*, 2018; LUCA *et al.*, 2019; HAN *et al.*, 2018; HERREMA and NIESS, 2020; RODACKI *et al.*, 2022).

In some cases, DM can be triggered by an imbalance in the gut microbiota, since it interacts with the diet and affects intestinal permeability, insulin sensitivity, inflammation regulation, glucose and lipid metabolism, and the body's immune response (HAN *et al.*, 2018; LIU, XU and ZHOU, 2019; HERREMA and NIESS, 2020; PACHOŃSKI *et al.*, 2021; CORTES *et al.*, 2021).

Blood glucose changes are related to long-term damage, such as predisposition to inflammation, dysfunction and insufficiency of various organs, especially eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, blood vessels and can generate other diseases that will be associated with DM (GOMES and ACCARDO, 2019; HERREMA and NIESS, 2020; SOUZA and OLIVEIRA, 2020; CORTES *et al.*, 2021; IDF, 2021; WHO, 2022; FENG *et al.*, 2022; SDB, 2022). This way, blood glucose control maintains the balance of microorganisms in tissues and organs.

Its treatment is based on palliative measures to reduce and delay the aggravations of the disease. It is necessary to change the lifestyle in ways such as: healthy diet, physical activity, maintenance of body weight, in addition to the use of medications that reduce blood glucose (GOMES and ACCARDO, 2019; SON *et al.*, 2022; IDF, 2021; WHO, 2022).

New effective and non-invasive therapeutic techniques that help in the control and treatment of DM have been researched to reduce signs and symptoms and facilitate living with the disease (LIRA *et al.*, 2018; ROSSANEIS *et al.*, 2019; ZHANG *et al.*, 2020).

In the survey of the researched literature, (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2017a; MARTINEZ, 2017b; BOSSA, 2021b) treatment protocols for type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM1) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2) have been identified. The objective of this study is to present the protocol to aid in the treatment of DM through the WB technique.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study conducted a literature review of an analytical conceptual method, which uses definitions of other authors (GIL, 1991) that converge with the objective proposed here to present the protocols and pairs described by the WB technique to help in the treatment of DM.

This research has an exploratory character, allowing an interaction between the theme and authors since the subject to be discussed is lacking in scientific literature. It is also qualitative, bringing a proximity to the subject to be familiarized, aiming to explore, prove or infer the hypotheses presented by literary research (GIL, 1991).

The literary research was based on books, handouts of the MB courses and articles found in the databases of PubMed and SciElo, chosen for the evaluation, accessibility and scientific authenticity. The additional literature relevant to this work was added through individual research in the online library of the Magnetic Pair Institute (MPI).

For some searched terms, filters were used within the platforms in order to personalize the search. All material found was included in the analysis of the methods and was quantified and exposed in Table 1. (chart/table)

The researchers were responsible for searching, selecting, and reading the articles, books and handouts selected for the theoretical basis of MSC, DM (the different forms of diabetes mellitus were considered) and the WB technique.

The descriptors used were: Static magnetic field, Static magnetic fields (emf) + health effects, diabetes + SMF, Magnetic therapy, Diabetes mellitus, Diabetes

mellitus and microorganisms, Medicinal biomagnetism, Biomagnetic Pair. The terms were also used in the English language for the purpose of expanding the search and obtaining a greater number of materials.

The inclusion criteria used were: full articles, free of charge, publications within the established search period, primarily five years, obeying the criteria of articles with digital object identifier (DOI). For the foundation of the WB were contemplated all the material found referring to the technique based on its creator Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán and authors who follow his line.

To describe the results, the material was submitted to the following exclusion criteria: duplicate references, absence of DOI, with content determined from the title and abstract that did not meet the basis of the study and the inclusion criteria.

From the analysis of the studied content it was possible to elaborate a report of the MB treatment protocol and a flowchart with the step-by-step treatment of DM.

3. RESULTS

The references used were their search in the PubMed and SciELO databases. The additional literature was found in IPM's online library, books and handouts. We used 42 references described in Table 1.

Table 1: Result of the search for literary material

SEARCH TERMS	PLATFORM	FILTERS USED	DETECTED FILES	FILES USED	DELETED FILES
Static magnetic field	SciELO	–	15	0	15
	PubMed	–	0	0	0
Static magnetic fields (emf) +	SciELO	–	0	0	0

health effects	PubMed	5 years	9	3	6
diabetes + SMF	SciELO	-	0	0	0
	PubMed	5 years	11	4	7
Magnetic therapy	Book	-	1	1	0
Diabetes mellitus	SciELO	5 years; Portuguese; article; Brazil	389	5	384
	PubMed	Free full text, Clinical Trial, Randomized Controlled Trial, Systematic Review, in the last 5 years, Human, Portuguese.	20	1	19
Diabetes mellitus and microorganisms	SciELO	5 years	2	1	1
	PubMed	Free full text, Review, in the last 5 years, humans	41	6	35
Diabetes mellitus	Guidelines	-	6	6	0
Medicinal biomagnetism	SciELO	-	1	0	1
	PubMed	-	0	0	0
By biomagnético	SciELO	-	1	1	0

	PubMed	-	0	0	0
Biomagnetism pair	SciELO	-	0	0	0
	PubMed		9	1	8
Medicinal biomagnetism	Book	-	2	2	0
Medicinal Biomagnetism	Handout	-	8	8	0
Medicinal Biomagnetism; SMF	Biblioteca on-line IPM	-	2	2	0
Methodological reference	book	-	1	1	0
Total	-	-	518	42	476

Source: the authors

In view of the inexpressive number of scientific articles published in relation to the WB, books and handouts of free courses were mainly used to support the elaboration of the DM treatment protocol, using the MB, in total 11 references of relevance.

The use of the protocol applied by a biomagnetism therapist consists of complete screening, followed by screening for DM diseases, basic protocol, respiratory system (SIS), gastrointestinal SIS, urological SIS, neurological SIS, cardiological SIS, dermatological SIS, Psych emotional SIS, SIS deworming, Symptom (SIN) urinary tract infection, detoxification, kidney Left (E) – Duodenum, BMPs diabetogenic, BMPs hyperglycaemic, BMPs related to hepatitis, complete screening and follow-up (DURÁN, 2008; MARTINEZ, 2017a; MARTINEZ, 2017b; MARTINEZ, 2019; BOSSA, 2021b).

Script of the treatment protocol with Medicinal Biomagnetism for patients with diabetes mellitus

1. Complete Scanning (CS)

It consists of performing the physical examination to identify the personalized BMPs. The sequence of the examination (screening) occurs by the analysis of the symmetry or asymmetry of the lower limbs. Then follows the screening line in the order reservoir pairs, other pairs, tumor phenomena, vascular phenomena, other phenomena, potential spaces, types of flows, psych emotional problems, hormonal problems, organic/inorganic deficiency, intoxication/poisoning, spiritual/malignant, electromagnetic energy distribution centers (Chakras) and chromosomes (BOSSA, 2021b).

2. Screening for Diseases – Diabetes Mellitus

Protocol that serves as a facilitator for the management of the therapeutic plan of patients with DM, described in Table 2.

3. Checking

Check periodically if symptoms have improved and if there is a need for any further screening or use of any more MB protocols.

For a better visualization and understanding of the process, a flowchart was used, described in Figure 3 that demonstrates the step by step of the possibilities of using the technique, describing schematically the treatment protocol of the MB applied to patients with DM1 and DM2 described in the literature researched.

Figure 3: Treatment Protocol Flowchart for DM

Subtitle: SIS (System); SIN (Symptom); BMPs (Biomagnetic Pairs); 3D1 (3D Protocol – Movement 1); 3D2 (3D Protocol – Movement 2) – 3D (deinflames, detoxifies and deflates).

Source: the authors, adapted from Durán (2008), Martínez (2017a and 2017b) and Bossa (2021a).

We present in Chart 2 the MBPs that make up the protocols for the treatment of DM.

Table 2: BMPs used in the DM Treatment Protocol

BIOMAGNETIC PAIRS	BMP's ILUSTRADOS
BASIC PROTOCOL	
Liver – Liver Liver – Kidney (D) Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L) Spinal Bulb – Lumbar 3/4 Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (R/L)	

Scam – Challenge
 Hip (R/L) – Table R/L
 Cardia – Appendix
 Transverse Colon – Liver
 Thyroid (R/L) – Thyroid (CL)
 Vagina (R/L) – Vagina (CL) or Testicle
 (R/L) – Testicle (CL)
 Lumbar – Kidney (R/L)

SIS RESPIRATORY

Suprascapular (R/L) – Suprascapular (CL)
 Hip (R/L) – Hip (R/L)
 Coronary – Lung (L)
 Vagina (R/L) – Vagina (CL) OR Testicle
 (R/L) – Testicle (CL)
 Trachea S (R/L) – Trachea I (IPS)
 Carina (R/L) – Carina (CL)
 Larynx T – Larynx B
 Pericardium – Pericardium
 Retroaxillary (R/L) – Retroaxillary (CL)
 Popliteal (R/L) – Popliteal (CL)
 Preauricular T (R/L) – Preauricular B
 (IPS)

SIX GASTROINTESTINAL

Transverse Colon – Liver
 Cardia – Appendix
 Colon descending – Colon descending
 Tail of the pancreas – Liver
 Colon descending – Liver
 Stomach – Thymus
 Gluteum (R/L) – Gluteum (R/L)
 Pylorus – Liver
 Esophageal hiatus – Vagina (R/L) OR

Testicle (R/L)
 Transverse Stomach/Colon – Sacrum

UROLOGICAL SIX

Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)
 Bladder – Bladder
 Scam – Challenge
 Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (R/L)
 Colon descending – Colon descending
 Coccyx T – Coccyx B
 Urethra T – Urethra B
 Vagina (R/L) – Vagina (CL) OR Testicle (R/L) – Testicle (CL)
 Vas Deferente – Larynx
 Spermatic Conduit (R/L) – Spermatic Conduit (CL)

ADULT NEUROLOGICAL SYSTEM

Pineal powder – Bladder
 Occipital (R/L) – Occipital (CL)
 Spinal Bulb – Cerebellum
 Temporoccipital (R/L) – Temporoccipital (CL)
 Parietal (R/L) – Parietal (CL)
 Temporal (R/L) – Temporal (CL)
 Ear (R/L) – Ear (CL)
 Mastoid (R/L) – Mastoid (CL)
 Parietal (R/L) – Colon Transverse
 Anterior corpus callosum (R/L) – Posterior corpus callosum (IPS)
 Pineal – Spinal Bulb
 Pineal Post – Spinal Bulb
 Gluteum (R/L) – Gluteum (R/L)

Cardia – Temporal (R/L)
Armpit (R/L) – Armpit (CL)

CHILD NEUROLOGICAL SIS

Pineal powder – Bladder
Eye (R/L) – Eye (R/L)
Occipital (R/L) – Occipital (CL)
Spinal Bulb – Cerebellum
Temporooccipital (R/L) – Temporooccipital (CL)
Parietal (R/L) – Transverse Colon
Parietal (R/L) – Parietal (CL)
Ear (R/L) – Ear (CL)
Stomach – Adrenal
Thymus – Parietal (R/L)
Armpit (R/L) – Armpit (CL)

DERMATOLOGICAL SIS

Labial commissure (R/L) – Labial commissure (R/L)
Thymus – Parietal (R/L)
Stomach – Adrenals(C)
Appendix – Language (R/L)
Language (R/L) – Language (CL)
Pancreas Tip – Spleen
Scapula (R/L) – Scapula (R/L)
Bladder – Bladder
Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (R/L)
Pinta* – Kidney (R/L) *track all warts.

PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL SIX

<p>Patella (R) – Patella (L) (Fear)</p> <p>Liver – Heart (Wrath)</p> <p>Lung (R/L) – Spinal bulb (Sadness)</p> <p>Lung (R/L) – Lung (L) (Guilt)</p> <p>Heart – Pancreas (Envy)</p> <p>Spleen – Hypothalamus (Laziness)</p> <p>Thymus – Ovary (R/L) or Testicle (R/L) (Impatience)</p> <p>Stomach – Heart (Gula)</p> <p>Back of the hand (R) – Back of the hand (L) (Doubt)</p> <p>Back of the foot (R) – Back of the foot (L) (Doubt)</p>	
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SIS DESPARASITAÇÃO

<p>Gluteum (R/L) – Gluteum (R/L)</p> <p>Ischius (R/L) – Ischial (CL)</p> <p>Quadriceps (R/L) – Quadriceps (CL)</p> <p>Liver – Kidney (L)</p> <p>Pylorus – Liver</p> <p>Pylorus – Kidney (L)</p> <p>Duodenum – Tail of the Pancreas</p>	
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SIN URINARY TRACT INFECTION

<p>Scam – Challenge</p> <p>Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (R/L)</p> <p>Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)</p> <p>Bladder – Bladder</p> <p>Colon descending – Colon descending</p>	
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DETOXIFICATION

BASIC DETOX PROTOCOL

Liver – Liver
 Liver – Kidney (R)
 Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)

DETOXIFICATION PROTOCOL

Liver – Kidney (R)
 Liver – Liver
 Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)
 Pancreas (R/L) – Lung (CL)

BASIC PROTOCOL 1

Scam – Challenge
 Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus
 (CL)
 Transverse Colon – Liver
 Cardias – Appendix
 Post-pineal – Bladder

BASIC PROTOCOL

Liver – Liver
 Liver – Kidney (R)
 Spinal Bulb – Lumbar (3/4)
 Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus
 (CL)
 Scam – Challenge
 Hip (R/L) – Hip (R/L)
 Cardias – Appendix
 Transverse Colon – Liver
 Thyroid (R/L) – Thyroid (CL)
 Vagina (R/L) – Vagina (CL) (Testicles)
 Lumbar – Kidney (R/L)

3D PROTOCOL – MOVEMENT 1

Liver – Liver
 Liver – Kidney (R)
 Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)
 Spinal Bulb – Lumbar 3/4
 Scam – Challenge
 Supraspinatus (R) – Supraspinatus (L)

Dynamic:

Hip (R) – Hip (L)
 Transverse Colon – Liver
 Cardias – Appendix
 Thyroid (R) – Thyroid (L)
 Vagina (R) – Vagina (L) (Testicles)
 Lumbar – Kidney (R/L)
 Eye (R) – Eye (L)
 Patella (R) – Patella (L)

3D PROTOCOL – MOVEMENT 2

Liver – Liver
 Liver – Kidney (R)
 Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)
 Spinal Bulb – Lumbar 3/4
 Scam – Challenge
 Supraspinatus (R) – Supraspinatus (L)

Dynamic:

Hip (R) – Hip (L)
 Transverse Colon – Liver
 Colon descending – Colón descendiendo
 Thyroid (L) – Thyroid (R)
 Vagina (L) – Vagina (R) (Testicles)
 Lumbar – Kidney
 Eye (L) – Eye (R)
 Patella (L) – Patella (R)

EXTENDED BASIC PROTOCOL

Basic reservoirs

Cavities – Kidney (R/L)

Scar – Kidney (R/L)

Vagina (R/L) – Vagina (CL) (Testicles)

Basic Detox

Liver – Liver

Liver – Kidney (R)

Kidney (R/L) – Kidney (R/L)

Basic Column

Cervical – Sacro

Spinal Bulb – Lumbar 3/4

Protocolo Basic 1

Scam – Challenge

Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (CL)

Transverse Colon – Liver

Cardias – Appendix

Post-pineal – Bladder

Basic dysfunctional

Pineal – Pineal

Hipófise – Hipófise

Thyroid (R/L) – Thyroid (CL)

Paratireoides (R/L) – Paratireoide (CL)

Pylorus – Pylorus

PAIR BIOMAGNETIC

Kidney L – Duodenum

DIABETOGENIC BMPs (For treatment of T1D) – Viruses

Scam – Challenge

Pancreas – Pancreas

Duodenum – Duodenum

Armpit (R/L) – Armpit (CL)
Appendix – Language (R/L)
Thymus – Parietal (R/L)
Stomach – Supplytorrenais
Pancreatic Ligament – Spleen
Conduto of the Pancreas – Liver
Conduit of the Pancreas – Kidney (L)
Vesicle Conduit – Kidney (R)
Pancreatic Ligament – Colon descending
BMPs of pathogenic viruses (Chart 3)

HYPERGLYCEMIC BMPs (For treatment of T2DM) – Bacterium and Parasites

Bladder – Bladder
Cervical – Sacrum
Liver – Kidney (R)
Pancreas – Pancreas
Ridney (R/L) – Ridney (CL)
Spinal Bulb – Lumbar 3/4
Scapula (R/L) – Scapula (R/L)
Parotid (R/L) – Parotid (CL)
Supraspinatus (R/L) – Supraspinatus (R/L)
Larger Trocanter (R/L) – Major Trocanter (CL)
Hip (R/L) – Hip (CL)
Colon Descending – Colon Descending
Jaw (C/R/L) – Jaw (C/CL)
BMPs of pathogenic acidias (Chart 3)

Hepatitis BMPs

Hepatitis A – Colon descending – Liver
Hepatitis B – Pleura – Liver
Hepatitis C – Liver – Liver
Hepatitis D – Duodenum – Liver
Hepatitis E – Ascending Colon – Liver
Hepatitis G – Transverse Colon – Liver

Legend: R (right); L (left); CL (contralateral); IPS (ipsilateral); B (bottom); T (top); 3/4 (between lumbar vertebrae 3 and 4).

Source: the authors, adapted from Bossa (2021a).

We present the hyperglycemic and diabetogenic BMPs with the respective associated pathogens with a focus on the treatment of DM, according to Table 3.

Table 3: Description of BMPs related to pathogenic microorganisms included in the DM Treatment Protocol

DIABETOGENIC BMPs PATHOGENIC VIRUSES	PATHOGENIC BACTERIA HYPERGLYCEMIC BMPs
<p>Adductor – Adductor (HIV)</p> <p>Palatine Amygdala – Palatine Amygdala (Herpes Virus 2)</p> <p>Annex – Annex (Paramyxovirus)</p> <p>Anus – anus (papilloma virus)</p> <p>Appendix – Tongue (Smallpox Virus)</p> <p>Appendix – Femoral Vein (Vaccine Virus)</p> <p>Armpit – Armpit (Rabies Virus)</p> <p>Spinal bulb – Bladder (dengue hemorrhagic)</p> <p>Spinal bulb – Cerebellum (Newcastle virus)</p> <p>Renal Chalice – Ureter (Herpes Virus 5)</p> <p>Carina – Carina (foot-and-mouth disease virus)</p> <p>Sciatica – Sciatica (polio virus)</p> <p>Coccyx – Coccyx (Rotavirus)</p>	<p>Angle – Angle (Bacteroides Fragilis)</p> <p>Achilles – Achilles (Shigella)</p> <p>Spleen – Spleen (Yersinia Pestis)</p> <p>Spleen – Liver (Brucella Abortus)</p> <p>Bladder – Bladder (Streptococcus G)</p> <p>Brachial – Brachial (Streptococcus Pyogenes)</p> <p>Exchange – Exchange (Actinomyces)</p> <p>Head of Pancreas – Adrenals (Staph. Aureus Coag. Negative)</p> <p>Calcaneus – Calcaneus (Rickettsia)</p> <p>Renal Capsule – Renal Capsule (Proteus Mirabilis)</p> <p>Cardias – Adrenal (beta-hemolytic streptococcus)</p> <p>Tail of the Pancreas – Liver (Clostridium Botulinum)</p> <p>Cervical – Supraspinatus (Balatidium coli)</p> <p>Clitoris – Sacrum (Spirochetes)</p> <p>Ascending Colon – Kidney (Klebsiella)</p>

Ascending Colon – Descending Colon (Herpes Virus 1)	Pneumoniae)
Ascending Colon – Liver (Hepatitis E)	Descending Colon – Descending Colon (Enterobacter Cloacae)
Colon Descending – Liver (Hepatitis A)	Colon Descending – Kidney (Pasteurella)
Colon Sigmoid – Rectum (R-40 Virus)	Transverse Colon – Bladder (Vibrio Cholerae)
Transverse Colon – Liver (Hepatitis G)	Gallbladder Conduit – Kidney (Spirochetes)
Commissure – Commissure (Herpes Virus 4)	Pancreatic Conduit – Kidney (Spirochetes)
Duodenum – Liver (Hepatitis D)	Czech Contra – Czech Contra (Bordetella pertussis)
Stomach – Adrenals (Measles Virus)	Coronary – Lung (Streptococcus Pyogenes)
Liver – Liver (Hepatitis C)	Costal – Costal (Proteus Mirabilis)
Pituitary – Bladder (Dengue Virus)	Cost-hepatic – Cost-hepatic (Borrelia)
Hepatic Ligament – Kidney (Adenovirus)	Cranial – Cranial (Bacillus anthracis)
Pancreatic Ligament – Spleen (AH1N1/Nile Virus)	Deltoids – Deltoids (Treponema Pallidum)
Malar-Malar (Enterovirus)	Diaphragm – Kidney (Brucella Abortus)
External Manubrium – External Manubrium (Coxsackie Virus)	Dorsal – Low backKidney (Neisseria Meningitidis)
Inguinal Nerve – Liver (Roseola Virus)	Dorsal 2 – Dorsal 2 (Legionella)
Inguinal Nerve – Nervo Inguinal (HTLV)	Duodeno – Kidney (Chlamydia Trachomatis)
Occipital – Occipital (Epstein Barr virus)	Epiclon – Epiclon (Staphylococcus Albus)
Eye – Eye (Cytomegalovirus)	Scapula – Scapula (Mycobacterium Leprae)
Parietal – Parietal (encefalite viral)	Stomach – Pylorus (Clostridium perfringens)
Pineal – Spinal bulb (Guillain	Flank – flank (Yersinia enterocolitica)
	buttocks – Pilo (Veillonella)
	greater trochanter – greater trochanter (Salmonella Typhi)
	Esophageal Hiatus – Esophagus (Enterobacter Pneumoniae)
	Esophageal Hiatus – Testicle (Helicobacter Pylori)
	Indicator – Indicator (Escherichia Coli)

Barré Syndrome)
Orbital floor – Orbital floor (Orf virus)
Pleura – Liver (Hepatitis B)
Pleura – Pleura (Viral Pleurisy)
Polygon of Willis – Polygon of Willis (Reo Virus)
Tip of the Pancreas – Spleen (Common Wart)
Prostate – Rectum (Papilloma Virus)
Pudendal – Pudendal (caxumba)
Douglas Bag – Femoral Vein (Norwalk Virus)
Frontal Sinus – Frontal Sinus (Frontal Sinusitis)
Paranasal Sinuses – Paranasal Sinuses (Paranasal Sinusitis)
Suprapubic – Suprapubic (HTLV)
Temporary – Temporary (Polyoma Virus)
Thymus – Parietal (rubella virus)
Thymus – Rectum (HIV)
Thyroid – Spinal bulb (viral meningitis)
Trachea – Trachea (flu virus)
Minor Trochanter – Minor Trochanter (HIV)
Fallopian tube – Fallopian tube (Parvovirus)
Ulna – Ulna (herpes virus 3)
Ureter – Ureter (chickenpox virus)
Urethra – Urethra (Corona Virus)
Gallbladder – Kidney (Rhinovirus)

Lackidneyal – Lackidneyal (Haemophilus Influenzae)
Larynx – Larynx (Bordetella pertussis)
External Knee Ligament – Lumbar Quadratus (Streptococcus Agalactie)
Jaw – Jaw (Neisseria Gonorrhoeae)
Mediastinum – Mediastinum (Proteus mirabilis)
Eyelid – Eyelid (Moraxella Catarrhalis)
Pericardium – Pericardium (Staphylococcus aureus)
Perihepatic – Perihepatic (Morganella Tifo)
Pleura – Pleura (Pseudomonas Aeruginosa)
Cervical plexus – cervical plexus (Enterococcus faecalis)
Popliteal – Popliteal (Streptococcus Pneumoniae)
Pulse – Pulse (Rickettsia)
Lumbar Square – Lumbar Square (Treponema Pallidum)
Hip – Hip (Chlamydia Pneumoniae)
Fourth lumbar – Fourth lumbar (Neisseria Gonorrhoeae)
Isquiática branch – Isquiática branch (Streptococcus C)
Challenge – Challenge (Pseudomonas aeruginosa)
Kidney – Kidney (Clostridium Tetani)
Sacred – Sacred (Proteus mirabilis)
Subclavian – Subclavian (Corynebacterium Diphtheriae)
Supraspinatus – Supraspinatus (Mycobacterium Tuberculosis)

	Suprahepatic – Suprahepatic (Clostridium Malignum)
	Suprarenal – Rectum (Leptospira)
	Occipital time – Occipital time (Mycoplasma)
	Temporary – Temporary (Rickettsia Prowazecki)
	Testicle – Testicle (Yersinia pestis)
	Umerus – Umerus (Enterobacter pneumoniae)
	Vagina – Vagina (Yersinia Pestis)

Source: the authors, MARTÍNEZ (2017a)

4. DISCUSSION

The gut microbiota (IM) is made up of microorganisms vital for balancing metabolism and physiology in the human body. Its dysfunction has been related to one of the factors that provoke DM (HAN *et al.*, 2018; HERREMA and NIESS 2020). According to Herrema, and Niess (2020), the distribution of the intestinal microbial population varies throughout the intestine and according to each individual and their lifestyle. With the increased consumption of carbohydrates, fats and processed foods and with the significant reduction of fiber intake result in dysbiosis (imbalance of the microbiome).

The human microbiome is characterized by the sum of microorganisms that coexist in symbiosis with the human organism, where the body offers the ecological niche. In contrast, they aid in digestion, absorption of nutrients and other various functions (HERREMA and NIESS, 2020). They engage in metabolic processes in most external tissues and organs. The most diverse microbiomes in the human body are oral and intestinal, having a direct relationship with the health status of the individual (LIU, XU and ZHOU, 2019; PACHOŃSKI *et al.*, 2021; HERREMA and NIESS, 2020).

Given this situation we have to have a view of the set of microorganisms that coexist with us, not all of them are pathogenic and our study focuses on the treatment via MB of pathogenic microorganisms that favor the development of DM.

According to Toniolo (2018), infections related to DM involve fungi, bacteria, parasites and viruses related among the infectious biological agents, which is corroborated by Goiz in his proposals for treatment and identification of pathogens related to BMPs.

In line with WHO data, DM has been growing considerably and with serious consequences on the health of the population, in addition to generating high costs with its treatment (TONIOLO *et al.*, 2018; MORESCHI, 2018; IDF, 2021; WHO, 2022; LUCA, 2019).

Several researchers affirm that the magnetic or electrical stimulation of tissues and organs exerts toning or sedative effect according to the need to be adjusted in the body system (CRUZ, 2005; BROERINGMEYER, 1991; CARTER *et al.*, 2020; LI *et al.*, 2020; FENG *et al.*, 2022). Thus, some protocols for the treatment of some diseases, using the MB have already been described in the Biomagnetic Pairs Guides Level 1 and 2 of David Goiz Martínez as Basic Biomagnetic Pair Protocols. In these documents, the protocols are described through the compilation of the peers that most appeared in the consultations performed by Dr. Goiz Durán.

According to Martínez (2017a), these protocols were developed with the purpose of serving as quick reference guides to track the most important points associated with diseases and symptoms to treat different diseases prophylactically and laterally. However, he clarifies that protocols do not replace and are no more important than full screening.

The Par Magnético Institute (IPM) compiled these pairs contained in the Basic Biomagnetic Pair Protocols, described in the Guides, and modified the terms by detoxification protocols, Systems Screening (SIS), Symptom Screening (SIN) and Disease Protocol (BOSSA, 2021c).

Biomagnetists use the information contained in these guides as a basis to simplify understanding and efficiency in daily work for patient care. However, there is no official standardization, being in charge of each professional the form of presentation of this content in their courses, as well as in its practical use.

MB is still little known for being a relatively new technique. On October 10, 2022, it was 34 years since the discovery of the first BMP and on this same date the day of the Biomagnetist is celebrated informally. This technique is still under construction, so there is a long way to go before it becomes known and recognized by the general community.

The guidance of Dr. Goiz, as the creator of the technique, has always been to perform the complete screening. By proposing a protocol script for the treatment of DM, a way to transmit knowledge with concise didactics and standardization of action is sought.

Therefore, it is necessary to create, standardize and use treatment protocols, including to enable the effectiveness of the technique and the proof of its efficiency in improving the quality of life of patients.

According to the definition of the Ministry of Health, Integrative and Complementary Practices (PICS) are treatments that use therapeutic resources based on traditional knowledge to prevent various diseases. In some cases, they can also be used as palliative treatments in some chronic diseases (BRASIL, 2020).

The Unified Health System (SUS) offers the population, free of charge and integrally, 29 procedures of Integrative and Complementary Practices (PICS). These services can be found in Primary Health Care (BRASIL, 2020).

Through this, we seek the possibility of including Medicinal Biomagnetism in the National Policy of Integrative and Complementary Practices (PNPICS), for its offer to be expanded from private to public care, via SUS. In this way, the protocols can present more effective solutions for the care, seeking to increase the capillarity

and efficiency of the technique in the best possible way, in addition to having a cost and reduced side effects in relation to conventional treatments.

Thus, this study is dedicated to the presentation of a protocol that covers several protocols already known and validated by Martínez, seeking optimization and organization of therapy processes for the Biomagnetists. By combining the various protocols we have a synergy of actions that seeks to optimize time and reduce possible failures in treatment, in addition to respecting the individuality of the patient and its peculiarities.

Not all patients will undergo the treatments of all protocols, however Biomagnetists need to track each of them, ensuring that no BMP is disregarded. This search covers some gaps that can occur, always focusing on the search for excellence.

The protocols 24 Pancreas and 25 Pancreatic Fine Screening (BOSSA, 2021c) were evaluated and it was concluded that they should be incorporated into the DM treatment protocol, as it guarantees greater safety to the Biomagnetist in his screening. Thus, this study proposes the inclusion of Fine Screening in the DM treatment protocol, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Proposal to include the Fine Screening Protocol in the Treatment for DM.

FINE 24 – PÂNCREAS	
Pancreatic ampoule peripancreatic	
FINE 25 – PANCREATIC	

Source: the authors, adapted from Bossa (2021a).

Figure 4 describes the flowchart with the inclusion of fine screening in the DM treatment protocol.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the Proposed Treatment Protocol for DM

Subtitle: SIS (System); SIN (Symptom); BMPs (Biomagnetic Pairs); 3D1 (3D Protocol – Movement 1); 3D2 (3D Protocol – Movement 2).

Source: the authors, adapted from Durán (2008), Martínez (2017a and 2017b) and Bossa (2021a).

5. CONCLUSION

DM is a growing global public health problem that could be avoided by preventive measures and through better lifestyle. The MB has been shown to be a complementary and integrative technique with potential for prophylaxis and treatment in metabolic, endocrine, and pathogenic disorders. This study presented the description of the protocol to aid in the treatment of DM1 and DM2 through the MB technique. Such application is easy, low cost and with relatively fast results, non-invasive and with few side effects. Future research is necessary, using the protocol described to prove the therapeutic tool of MB in the aid of the treatment of DM and its associations.

6. FUTURE PROSPECTS

The present study suggests the application of this DM treatment protocol in groups of people, within the methodology normally accepted in scientific research to validate its results. In this way, the Biomagnetists could benefit from this work, facilitating the routine treatment of patients. This process could benefit patients, reducing complications resulting from the pathology, especially in primary care, with the reduction of demand and costs for the treatment of DM.

REFERENCES

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Apostila de Biomagnetismo Medicinal**. Cascavel/RS: Independent Publisher; Volume 1, Ed. 12. August – 2021a. Available in www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Access in: October/2022.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Protocolo de Rastreamento do Biomagnetismo Medicinal**. Cascavel/PR: Independent Publisher; Volume 1, Ed. 5 January – 2021b. Available in www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Access in: May/2022.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Biomagnetismo Medicinal Avançado**. 2. ed. Rattlesnake: Magnetic Pair, 281 p., 2021c.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Descrição dos Pares Biomagnéticos**. Magnetic Pair, 4th Ed. Rattlesnake, 2019.

BRAZIL. Ministry of Health. Minister's Office. **Práticas Integrativas e Complementares** (PICS). Brasilia, 2020. <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/assuntos/saude-de-a-a-z/p/praticas-integrativas-e-complementares-pics-1> accessed 10/17/2022.

BROERINGMEYER, Richard. **Principios de la Terapia Magnetica/Bio-magnetismo**. Health Industries, Inc, 1991.

CARTER, Calvin S; HUANG, Sunny C; SEARBY, Charles C; SPITZ, Douglas R; ABEL; Dale E; SHEFFIELD, Val C Exposure to Static Magnetic and Electric Fields Treats Type 2 Diabetes. **Cell Metab**. 2020. *Metabolismo celular*, 32 (6), 1076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2020.11.001>

CASTEJÓN, Enrique de Juan Gonzalez, **Efectos Biológicos de la Terapia del Par Biomagnético**, Tesis Doctoral, Alcalá de Henares, 2015.

CÔRTEZ, Debora; DE CENA, Jéssica; MARCONATTO, Letícia; GUIMARÃES, Maria do Carmo; GRISI, Daniela; DE OLIVEIRA, Laudimar; SALES, Loise; BORGES, Luiz Gustavo; DAMÉ-TEIXEIRA, Nailê. Clinical parameters of individuals with periodontitis and Diabetes Mellitus reveals signatures of the minority microbiota in saliva. **SciELO Preprints**, 2021. DOI: 10.1590/SciELOPreprints.3093. Disponível em: <https://preprints.scielo.org/index.php/scielo/preprint/view/3093>. Acesso em: 12 out. 2022.

CRUZ, Juan Alberto Leyva. **Images from magnetic sources using a multichannel system of magneto-resistive sensors**. 2005. Thesis (PhD in Physics Applied to Medicine and Biology) – Faculty of Philosophy, Sciences and Letters of Ribeirão Preto, University of São Paulo, Ribeirão Preto, 2005. doi:10.11606/T.59.2005.tde-11092007-233418. Access in: 2022-05-24.

DURÁN, Isaac. El Fenomeno Tumoral. Loja, Ecuador, p.8-14, 2003.

DURÁN, Isaac Goiz. **El Par Biomagnético**. 5. ed. Chapingo, México D. F.: Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, p.1-171, 2008.

FENG, Chuanlin., Yu, Biao., Song, Chao., Wang, Junjun., Zhang, Lei., Ji, Xinmiao., Wang, Ying., Fang, Yanwen., Liao, Zhongcai., Wei, Min., & Zhang, Xin. Static Magnetic Fields Reduce Oxidative Stress to Improve Wound Healing and Alleviate Diabetic Complications. **Cells**, 11(3), 443, 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11030443>

FILHO, Ruy Lira das Silva; ALBUQUERQUE, Luciano; CAVALCANTI, Saulo; et.al. Tratamento farmacológico da hiperglicemia no DM2. **Diretriz Oficial da Sociedade Brasileira de Diabetes**. 2022. DOI: 10.29327/557753.2022-10, ISBN: 978-65-5941-622-6. <https://Diretriz.Diabetes.Org.Br/Classificacao-Do-Diabetes/>

FRANK, Bryan L. Biomagnetic Pair Therapy and Typhoid Fever: A Pilot Study. **Medical Acupuncture**, [S.L.], v. 29, n. 5, p. 308-312, out. 2017. Mary Ann Liebert Inc. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/acu.2017.1253>.

GIL, Antônio Carlos. **Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa**. São Paulo: Atlas, 1991.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Guía del Pares Biomagnéticos primer nivel**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 142 p., 2017a.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Guía del Pares Biomagnéticos segundo nivel**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 120 p., 2017b.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Manual del biomagnetista**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 169 p., 2018.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Protocolos de Biomagnetismo**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 2019.

GOMES, Bárbara Festa; ACCARDO, Camila de Melo. Immunoinflammatory mediators in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus. **Einstein** (São Paulo), São Paulo, v. 17, n. 1, eRB4596, Feb. 2019.
https://doi.org/10.31744/einstein_journal/2019RB4596

HAN, Hui, Yuying Li, Jun; FANG, Gang Liu, Jie; YIN, Tiejun Li, and Yulong YIN. Gut Microbiota and Type 1 Diabetes. **International Journal of Molecular Sciences** 19, no. 4: 995. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19040995>

HERREMA, Hilde, NIESS, Jan Hendrick. Intestinal microbial metabolites in human metabolism and type 2 diabetes. **Diabetologia** 63, 2533–2547, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-020-05268-4>

Internacional Diabetes Federation. IDF Diabetes Atlas [Internet]. 10th Ed. Brussels: **International Diabetes Federation**; 2021.

https://diabetesatlas.org/idfawp/resourcefiles/2021/07/IDF_Atlas_10th_Edition_2021

JIMENO, Rosel Ucles; PENA, María del Pilar Amaro; BAENA, Marina Domingo. Evolución de la glucosa en pacientes geriátricos diabéticos con la aplicación del par biomagnético. **Gerokomos**, Barcelona, v. 25, n. 3, p. 107-110, sept. 2014. Disponible en <http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1134-928X2014000300005&lng=es&nrm=iso>. Acedido em 25 jul. 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4321/S1134-928X2014000300005>.

LI, Qin; FANG, Yanwen; WU, Ningzi; GU, Lili; LI, Hongxing; LIAO, Zhongcai; LIU, Zhongcai; FANG, Zhicai; & ZHANG, X Xinyue. Protective Effects of Moderate Intensity Static Magnetic Fields on Diabetic Mice. **Bioelectromagnetics**, 41(8), 598–610. Nov. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bem.22305>

LIMA, Luciano Ramos; FUNGHETTO, Silvana Schwerz; VOLPE, Cris Renata Grou; SANTOS, Walterlânia Silva; FUNEZ, Mani Indiana; STIVAL, Marina Morato. Qualidade de vida e o tempo do diagnóstico do diabetes mellitus em idosos. **Revista Brasileira de Geriatria e Gerontologia**, v. 21, p. 180-190, 2018. Disponível Em: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/1981-22562018021.170187>

LIRA, José Cláudio Garcia; OLIVEIRA, Jales Fhelipe de Sousa Fernandes; SOUZA, Maria Amélia de; ARAÚJO, Márcio Flávio Moura de; DAMASCENO, Marta Maria Coelho; FREITAS, Roberto Wagner Júnior Freire de. Prevalência da Síndrome Metabólica E De Seus Componentes Em Pessoas Com Diabetes Mellitus Tipo 2.

Texto & Contexto – Enfermagem [Online]. 2018, V. 27, N. 3 [Acessado 3 Abril 2022], E3900016. Disponível Em: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/0104-070720180003900016>

LIU, Yunkun; XU, X Xin; & ZHOU, Xuedong. Potential application of human microbiomes in the diagnosis and treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. **Jornal de Estomatologia da China Ocidental**, 37 (5), 556–562. Apr. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.7518/hxkq.2019.05.020>

LUCA, Maria; DI MAURO, Maurizio; DI MAURO, Mauro & LUCA, **Antonina**. Neuropsychiatric Disturbances and Diabetes Mellitus: The Role of Oxidative Stress. **Medicina oxidativa e longevidade celular**, apr.2019, 4730539. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4730539>

MOLINARI, Claudio; STOPPA, Ian; LIMARDO, Nicola; UBERTI, Francesca. Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Protective Patches on Acupoints to Preserve the Bioenergetic Status against Magnetic Fields. **Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM**, 2018, 4732130. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4732130>

MORESCHI, Claudete et al. Estratégias Saúde da Família: perfil/qualidade de vida de pessoas com diabetes. **Revista brasileira de enfermagem**, v. 71, p. 2899-2906, 2018.

Organização Mundial da Saúde (OMS) (2022). [Acessado 3 Abril 2022], <https://www.paho.org/pt/noticias/15-4-2021-oms-lanca-novo-pacto-global-para-acelerar-acoes-combate-diabetes>.

PACHOŃSKI, Marek; KOCZOR-ROZMUS, Aleksandra; MOCNY-PACHOŃSKA, Katarzyna; ŁANOWY, Patrycja; MERTAS, Anna and JAROSZ-CHOBOT, Przemysława. Oral microbiota in children with type 1 diabetes mellitus”. **Pediatric Endocrinology Diabetes and Metabolism** 27 (2): 100-108. Apr. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5114/pedim.2021.104343>

RODACKI Melaine; TELES Milena; GABBAY Monica; MONTENEGRO Renan; BERTOLUCI Marcello. Classificação do diabetes. **Diretriz Oficial da Sociedade Brasileira de Diabetes**.2022. DOI: 10.29327/557753.2022-1, ISBN: 978-65-5941-622-6. <https://Diretriz.Diabetes.Org.Br/Classificacao-Do-Diabetes/>

ROSSANEIS, Mariana Angela et al. Fatores Associados Ao Controle Glicêmico De Pessoas Com Diabetes Mellitus. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva** [Online]. 2019, V. 24, N. 3 [Acessado 3 Abril 2022], Pp. 997-1005. Disponível Em: <<https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232018243.02022017>>. ISSN 1678-4561.

SHANG, Wenlong., Chen, Guilin., Li, Yinxiu., Zhuo, Yujuan., Wang, Yuhong., Fang, Zhicai., Yu, Ying., & Ren, Huiwen. Static Magnetic Field Accelerates Diabetic Wound Healing by Facilitating Resolution of Inflammation. **Journal of diabetes research**, 2019, 5641271. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5641271>

Sociedade Brasileira De Diabetes [Homepage na internet]. **Diretrizes Da Sociedade Brasileira De Diabetes** 2021-2022. São Paulo: Editora Clannad; 2022. <https://Diretriz.Diabetes.Org.Br/>

SOUZA, Claudio Lima; OLIVEIRA, Marcio Vasconcelos. Fatores associados ao descontrole glicêmico de diabetes mellitus em pacientes atendidos no Sistema Único de Saúde no Sudoeste da Bahia. **Cadernos Saúde Coletiva**, v. 28, p. 153-164, 2020.

TONIOLO, Antonio; CASSANI, Gianluca; PUGGIONI, Anna; ROSSI, Agostino; COLOMBO, Alberto; ONODERA, Takashi; FERRANNINI, Ele. The diabetes pandemic and associated infections: suggestions for clinical microbiology. **Reviews in Medical Microbiology**: – Volume 30 – Issue 1 – p 1-17 January 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MRM.000000000000155>

ZHANG, Bing; XIE, Yangli; NI, Zhenhong; CHEN, Lin. Effects and Mechanisms of Exogenous Electromagnetic Field on Bone Cells: **A Review. Bioelectromagnetics**, v.41(4), p.263–278, May 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bem.22258>

ZHANG, Hao Gan Lu; ZHU, Xiaoquan Wang Jun., HAN, Licun Cheng Peng; ZHANG, Jing, Da Xiaodong; SHAN, Qingshun. Moderate-intensity 4mT static magnetic fields prevent bone architectural deterioration and strength reduction by stimulating bone formation in streptozotocin-treated diabetic rats. **Bone**, 107, 36–44, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bone.2017.10.024>

¹Studian Graduate Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health, Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and Education of São Paulo – FGE. SP, Brazil.

²Co-supervising Professor Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health, Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and Education of São Paulo – FGE. SP, Brazil.

³Advising Professor Program in Biomagnetism and Bioenergy Applied to Health, Par Magnético Institute – IPM / Faculty of Governance, Engineering and Education of São Paulo – FGE. SP, Brazil.

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